

crystallised from boiling water (charcoal) as fine colourless needles, m. p. 217° (Found : N, 11.45 ; Cl, 14.21. $C_8H_9O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 11.26 ; Cl, 14.28 per cent).

(b). *p*-Thioglycolylaminobenzene Sulphonamide.—The above compound (1 mol., finely powdered) was suspended in alcohol (95%) and heated to 60-70° on a water-bath. Powdered ammonium thiocyanate (1 mol.) was added to it and the mixture was kept at this temperature with stirring for 3 hours. A pasty mass was obtained. It was triturated for one hour with water in a mortar and the separated solid was filtered, washed with water several times and then transferred to a flask and heated with excess of dilute ammonia on a water-bath till almost the whole of it went into solution. The solution was filtered, the filtrate cooled in ice and then acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid till a rose colour developed with methyl orange solution. The precipitate separating was filtered, washed with water and then crystallised from methyl alcohol (charcoal) in white needles, m. p. 264° (decomp.). (Found : N, 11.49 ; S, 25.53. $C_8H_{10}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 11.38 ; S, 25.61 per cent).

(c). *p*-Aurothioglycolylaminobenzene Sulphonamide ($NH_2.SO_2.C_6H_4.NHCOCH_2.SAu$).—The thioglyco-sulphonamidobenzanilide was dissolved in alcohol with warming and the solution was added to a solution of aurous bromide in alcohol (95%), prepared by passing sulphur dioxide through an alcoholic solution of potassium auribromide till the solution was colourless. The white precipitate that was formed was allowed to settle in the dark, then filtered, washed several times with water to remove sulphur dioxide, washed three times with alcohol (95%) and then thrice with absolute alcohol and finally thrice with petroleum ether and then dried in a vacuum desiccator in the dark. (Found : Au, 43.83. $C_8H_9O_3N_2S_2Au$ requires Au, 44.57 per cent).

Aurothioglycolylhomosulphanilamide ($NH_2.SO_2.C_6H_4.CH_2.NHCOCH_2.SAu$)

Homosulphanilamide (1 mol.) was dissolved in alcohol (95%) and chloroacetic acid (1 mol.) dissolved in alcohol (95%) was added to it in small quantities with stirring, keeping the temperature below 20°. After the addition was over, the mixture was kept at 20° for 3 hours, when a pasty mass was obtained. It was then heated to 60°-70° on a water-bath and powdered ammonium thiocyanate (1 mol.) was added to it with stirring. At first a solution was obtained and then after some time a precipitate began to appear. When the precipitation was complete, the mixture was triturated with water and proceeding in the same way as in the previous case, the thiol compound was obtained, m. p. 193-94° (Found : N, 10.88 ; S, 24.53. $C_9H_{12}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 10.77 ; S, 24.61 per cent). The gold compound was prepared from the thiol derivative as in the previous case as a white powder. (Found : Au, 42.79. $C_9H_{11}O_3N_2S_2Au$ requires Au, 43.20 per cent).

p-Aminobenzene Sulphon-(aurothioglycol) amide ($NH_2.C_6H_4.SO_2.NHCOCH_2.SAu$)

p-Acetamidobenzene sulphonamide (1 mol.) was treated with chloroacetyl chloride (1.25 mol.) in acetone solution. The chloroacetyl derivative, thus obtained, was hydrolysed with dilute caustic soda solution in the customary way and on just neutralising with dilute hydrochloric acid, the free base was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol in needles. (Found : N, 11.38 ; Cl, 14.19. $C_8H_9O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 11.26 ; Cl, 14.28 per cent).

The chloro compound was treated with ammonium thiocyanate as usual and the

thioglycolamide was obtained in white crystals darkening above 300°. (Found : N, 11.43 ; S, 25.57. $C_8H_{10}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 11.38 ; S, 25.61 per cent).

This thio compound on treatment with aurous bromide in the usual manner gave the gold compound as a white powder. (Found: Au, 43.42 $C_8H_9O_3N_2S_2Au$ requires Au, 44.57 per cent)

p-Aurothioglycolylaminobenzene Sulphonbenzamide ($C_6H_5CONH.SO_2.C_6H_4.NHCOCH_2.SAu$)

Sulphanilylbenzamide was treated with chloroacetyl chloride in the usual way. The chloroacetyl derivative thus obtained was treated with ammonium thiocyanate in the customary way and the thiol compound was obtained. (Found : N, 8.11 ; S, 18.42. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4N_2S_2$ requires N, 8.00 ; S, 18.3 per cent).

From the thiol compound the gold derivative was obtained in the usual manner as a white powder. (Found : Au, 35.48. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4N_2S_2Au$ requires Au, 36.08 per cent).

Aurothioglyco-sulphathiazole

Sulphathiazole was treated with chloroacetyl chloride as before and the chloroaceto derivative was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m. p. 237° (decomp.). (Found : N, 12.71 ; Cl, 10.68. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2S_2Cl$ requires N, 12.67 ; Cl, 10.70 per cent).

From this chloro compound the thiol derivative was obtained in the usual way. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate in slender needles. (Found : N, 12.89 ; S, 29.03. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 12.76 ; S, 29.18 per cent).

Proceeding in the usual manner the gold compound was prepared from the thiol derivative. (Found : Au, 36.79. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2S_2Au$ requires Au, 37.52 per cent).

Aurothioglycol-3:5-dibromoanilide

3:5-Dibromoaniline (m. p. 56-58°) was prepared according to the method of Holleman (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1906, II, 771) from *p*-nitroaniline, and treated with chloroacetic acid as usual. The reaction product was directly reacted with ammonium thiocyanate to get the thioglyco-3:5-dibromoanilide. (Found: N, 4.49 ; S, 9.86. $C_8H_7ONSBr_2$ requires N, 4.31 ; S, 9.84 per cent). Its gold compound has not yet been isolated in pure state.